

Inside our invisible bubble: A review of developmental and neural perspectives of peripersonal space in Autism

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Abstract

This review explores how Peripersonal Space (PPS)—the dynamic multisensory interface surrounding the body—is shaped in autism, a neurodevelopmental disability characterized by distinct sensory, motor, and social challenges. Atypical PPS dimensions in autistics, such as reduced flexibility and altered modulation, are linked to heightened sensory sensitivities, spatial navigation difficulties, and increased anxiety in social contexts. Neuroimaging studies indicate alterations in the premotor and parietal cortices as well as atypical thalamocortical connectivity, providing a neural basis for these differences. Drawing on neuroscience and developmental research, this review highlights how PPS evolves across the lifespan in autism, influencing everyday behaviors from infancy through old age. By integrating contemporary theories of PPS with empirical findings, we identify mechanisms that may underlie altered PPS representations and discuss their real-world implications. Advanced methodologies—most notably virtual reality (VR) and augmented reality (AR)—are accelerating PPS research by offering immersive, customizable environments for assessing sensory integration, yet limitations persist. Sampling biases, especially the exclusion of higher-support-needs individuals, hinder the generalizability of current findings. To address these challenges, we emphasize the importance of interdisciplinary collaboration, inclusive research designs, and the active participation of autistic individuals. A nuanced understanding of PPS can inform tailored interventions—such as sensory-friendly environments and the development of training strategies to enhance PPS flexibility—that improve quality of life. Ultimately, by bridging laboratory discoveries with clinical applications, PPS research can not only deepen our scientific understanding of autism but also foster greater social inclusion and practical support for the autistic community.

Key Words: *Autism, Disability, Motor coordination, Multisensory integration, Peripersonal space, Sensory processing, Spatial navigation, Social interaction*

Introduction

When a ball is thrown unexpectedly in your vicinity at a park (Figure 1a), you'll react only if you perceive that it will enter your Peripersonal Space (PPS) — the area immediately surrounding our bodies (Figure 1b) within which we perceive objects and events that may interact with us.¹ Inside this PPS zone, multisensory neurons are more responsive to stimuli, speeding reaction times. The plasticity of these neurons creates an adaptive, dynamic space that can adjust in size and shape (Figure 1b) based on context and

experience.² As a perceptual construct, PPS² is distinct from and not to be confused with the social constructs of Personal Space or Interpersonal Space (Figure 1c). Personal space is the physical space surrounding an individual that they consider to be their own and do not want others to invade without permission, while interpersonal space is the physical distance maintained between individuals that is comfortable for their social interactions.^{3–5}

Exploring these concepts further, this review paper explores PPS with a focus on its relationship to

Figure 1. Dynamics and contextualization of peripersonal space (PPS). (a) Illustration of the perception of an external object (a ball) approaching the body, demonstrating the role of PPS in detecting and responding to potential interactions within the immediate surrounding environment. (b) Visualization of the PPS as a dynamic, multisensory boundary surrounding the body, highlighting its capacity to contract or expand based on environmental and contextual factors, such as the proximity or relevance of external stimuli. (c) Representation of social constructs like personal space and interpersonal space, contrasting these culturally and contextually influenced distances with the perceptual construct of PPS. Figure b was created using BioRender.com.

autism, a group uniquely affected by this perceptual construct. Autism is a neurodevelopmental disability characterized by difficulties in social communication and interaction, restricted and repetitive behaviors, and sensory sensitivities.⁶ Research suggests that autistics may experience alterations in PPS, potentially contributing to their sensory and social difficulties.⁷ Differences in PPS between autistics and neurotypicals have been observed, although the nature and implications of these differences are still being explored.^{8,9}

This review aims to synthesize existing research on PPS and autism, enhancing our understanding of how alterations in PPS might influence the sensory and social experiences of autistic individuals. By integrating contemporary theories of PPS with findings from autism research, this paper seeks to elucidate the mechanisms through which PPS might differ in autism and the implications of these differences. The sections that follow will detail the neural basis of PPS, its behavioral implications, and the unique ways PPS manifests across different stages of life for autistics. By bridging neuroscientific research with clinical observations, the review underscores the importance of a nuanced understanding of PPS in designing effective therapeutic strategies tailored

to the specific needs of the autism community.

This review uses person-first language (e.g., “person with autism, person with disability”) and identity first language (e.g., “autistic, disabled”) interchangeably.¹⁰

PPS and multisensory integration in autism

Our understanding of PPS has evolved from being viewed merely as a defensive mechanism to a dynamic multisensory-motor interface that facilitates interaction with the environment.¹¹ PPS plays a critical role in motor control and social interactions by linking the body to its surroundings. It enables obstacle avoidance, object manipulation, and social engagement.^{12,13} For example, in the case of a ball approaching (Figure 1a), the perception of a PPS intrusion might trigger either a defensive response, such as dodging the ball, or a goal-directed action, such as catching and throwing it back. This active interface highlights how cognitive processes and physical experiences are deeply intertwined, emphasizing that our thoughts and actions are rooted in interactions with the world.¹⁴

Figure 2. Neural representations of PPS in EEG approximation. This figure illustrates the cortical regions potentially activated during PPS-related tasks as detected through EEG, focusing on both functional localization (a) and electrode mapping (b). Figure (a) highlights the superficial areas of the frontal and parietal lobes (b) maps EEG electrode positions corresponding to these areas, emphasizing the spatial approximation inherent in surface-level recordings. While EEG offers valuable insights into temporal dynamics, its spatial resolution is limited to superficial regions, necessitating complementary neuroimaging techniques to resolve deeper neural structures. Deeper structures, including the insular cortex and basal ganglia, are critical for PPS, but their contribution to the EEG signal remains unresolved. Figure a was created using biorender.com.

PPS in Autism: Challenges and Implications

In autism, PPS exhibits distinct characteristics that contribute to challenges in social and environmental interactions. Research indicates that autistics often have a smaller and less flexible PPS compared to neurotypicals, which may lead to difficulties in adjusting body boundaries in dynamic contexts.⁸ These alterations are particularly evident in social environments that demand rapid adaptations, such as spontaneous conversations or group activities. The reduced adaptability of PPS not only impedes effective interaction but also influences social integration and emotional well-being, highlighting the broader impact of PPS differences on autistic experiences.¹⁵

Sensory Processing and Reactivity in Autism

The reduced adaptability of PPS in autism is closely linked to atypical sensory processing, which shapes how individuals perceive and respond to their surroundings. Autism, as a

multifaceted neurodevelopmental disability, presents a spectrum of sensory and behavioral differences. Atypical sensory processing—characterized by hyper-reactivity, hypo-reactivity, and context-dependent variations—plays a significant role in shaping daily functioning and social interactions.^{16,17}

Sensory reactivity, in particular, refers to the immediate behavioral responses to stimuli within the natural environment. This is distinct from other measurable aspects of sensory processing, such as perceptual acuity, which focuses on detecting the presence or features of sensory input rather than behavioral responses. Reactivity in autism reflects perceptual differences that alter how sensory stimuli are experienced and acted upon, potentially leading to responses that seem disproportionate to the stimulus.¹⁸ For example, heightened sensitivity to specific textures or sounds might result in sensory-avoidant behaviors, while

reduced sensitivity could manifest as sensory-seeking actions.¹⁹ These patterns necessitate personalized intervention strategies to address sensory preferences and challenges effectively.²⁰ Acknowledging both sensory reactivity and perceptual variations is essential for developing comprehensive supports tailored to the unique sensory profiles of autistic individuals.

Multisensory Integration and Temporal Dynamics

Sensory reactivity patterns directly influence the integration of multisensory inputs, a process critical for maintaining a cohesive perception of space and interaction within the PPS. Multisensory integration—the ability to combine tactile, visual, and auditory inputs into a unified spatial representation—forms the basis for dynamic and adaptive PPS boundaries. In autism, disruptions in sensory processing often impair this integration, resulting in PPS boundaries that are either overly rigid or excessively variable.²¹ Temporal dynamics are a key aspect of multisensory integration, as precise neural timing ensures that sensory inputs are effectively synchronized.

Altered neural timing in autism, such as delayed synchronization between auditory and tactile inputs, exacerbates challenges in combining sensory inputs, leading to inconsistencies in spatial awareness and motor responses.¹⁸ Autistics exhibit wider temporal binding windows, integrating sensory stimuli over a longer timeframe, which can lead to difficulties in distinguishing whether two sensory events are occurring simultaneously or sequentially.²² This altered temporal integration further contributes to challenges in predicting and responding to environmental stimuli efficiently. For example, these delays may hinder the ability to react to rapidly approaching objects or engage smoothly in social interactions requiring quick adjustments to spatial boundaries. Struggles with synchronizing sensory events occurring in rapid succession further impede the ability to respond effectively to environmental stimuli. This foundational disruption in sensory timing influences the development of PPS across the lifespan, emphasizing the need for targeted interventions

to enhance sensory synchronization and improve multisensory integration in autism.

Neural basis of PPS in autism

PPS relies on a dynamic network of interconnected brain regions that integrate sensory and motor information. In the general population, key areas involved include the premotor cortex (PMC), essential for processing stimuli within PPS and planning motor responses¹¹; the parietal cortex, which integrates multisensory inputs for spatial mapping (Makin et al., 2007); and the superior temporal sulcus (STS), crucial for combining auditory and visual information and predicting object trajectories.²³

Electroencephalography (EEG) evidence provides a window into these dynamics by highlighting the involvement of cortical regions such as the premotor cortex (PMC), parietal lobes, and frontal areas.²⁴ Figure 2 illustrates the superficial regions activated during PPS tasks, with EEG mapping potentially indicating temporal dynamics despite limitations in spatial resolution. However, complementary imaging methods are necessary to explore deeper structures like the basal ganglia and insula, which also contribute to PPS processing.²¹

In autism, these mechanisms are notably altered. Reduced activity in the PMC and parietal cortex correlates with challenges in processing sensory information and interacting with the environment.⁴ Atypical connectivity between the thalamus—especially the pulvinar—and cortical areas further disrupts sensory integration, contributing to sensory sensitivities frequently reported by autistic individuals.^{18,25}

The pulvinar plays a key role in regulating attentional salience and sensory gating, and its altered function may lead to inefficient filtering of relevant vs. irrelevant sensory information, affecting PPS adaptability. Intracortical differences, particularly reduced connectivity between the premotor and parietal cortices, further impair real-time multisensory integration and motor planning, reinforcing the rigidity of PPS boundaries.²⁶

Figure 3. Comparative developmental trajectories of PPS in non-autistic and autistic populations.

This conceptual diagram highlights key developmental differences in sensory integration, motor development, and social interaction, emphasizing how these factors evolve differently in autistic individuals.

This distinction highlights how thalamocortical alterations primarily disrupt sensory regulation, while intracortical differences impair higher-order sensorimotor integration, both contributing to PPS inflexibility in autism.

EEG studies in neurotypical individuals show that frontoparietal networks rapidly recalibrate PPS boundaries based on prior sensory input, allowing real-time adaptation to environmental changes.⁸ This flexibility supports efficient multisensory integration and motor coordination. In autism, these rapid recalibrations are diminished, with EEG studies indicating reduced neural modulation and weaker PPS boundary adjustments in response to shifting sensory contexts.^{24,27} This rigidity in sensory processing may underlie difficulties in adapting to dynamic environments, impacting both motor coordination and social interaction.

Addressing these differences through interventions

targeting sensory integration and motor planning has the potential to enhance adaptive PPS functions in autism. Advances in VR and EEG methodologies promise to further uncover the real-time neural dynamics of PPS, providing insights for therapeutic innovation. Figure 2 exemplifies how EEG can map the cortical areas involved, emphasizing the role of such tools in bridging neuroscience with clinical applications.^{8,28} Interventions aimed at increasing PPS flexibility could improve spatial awareness, reduce sensory overload, and enhance motor coordination, ultimately supporting smoother social interactions and navigation in dynamic environments. VR-based training, in particular, offers a scalable and customizable approach to reinforcing real-time multisensory integration, making it a promising tool for intervention.

PPS across the lifespan

Across the lifespan, the integration of multiple

sensory inputs remains crucial for the effective functioning of PPS. This integration is particularly challenging in autism, where atypical sensory processing disrupts the usual development and functionality of PPS. Unlike the relatively predictable maturation of sensory processing in neurotypical development, which enhances sensory integration and regulation over time^{29,30} autistic individuals often experience a more variable and individualized trajectory.³¹ For instance, sensory aversions present in early childhood may diminish during adolescence or transform into sensory-seeking behaviors, while others may develop heightened sensitivities with age.^{32,33} These unique developmental patterns emphasize the need for tailored interventions to support the sensory and motor needs of autistic individuals at each life stage.^{18,25} Figure 3 illustrates the developmental differences in PPS across the lifespan between non-autistic and autistic populations, highlighting the unique sensory, motor, and social challenges faced by autistic individuals.

Infancy

PPS begins forming early, with infants demonstrating integrated sensory processing by three months of age.³⁴ This stage marks the transition from reflexive behaviors to intentional actions, with PPS playing a key role in directing attention to nearby events and fostering caregiver interactions.³⁵ Positive caregiver interactions, such as during breastfeeding, influence PPS boundaries, promoting sensory-motor learning essential for survival and development.

In autistic infants, disrupted sensory integration may delay or alter PPS formation. Variability in tactile and visual processing has been linked to altered neural activation in key sensory areas.¹⁸ These can affect early social behaviors, such as joint attention and turn-taking, which rely on consistent sensory responses within PPS.³⁶ Functional implications include challenges in reaching behaviors, feeding routines, and forming secure attachments, highlighting the cascading effects of early PPS alterations.

Childhood

As mobility increases, children refine their PPS through multisensory integration, enhancing motor coordination and spatial understanding.³⁷ Visual-tactile experiences and spatial routines with objects and/or social partners, such as pointing or counting, further enhance PPS development, supporting motor and cognitive skills.^{38,39}

For autistic children, hypersensitivity or hyposensitivity to sensory stimuli can disrupt these processes, complicating navigation and social interactions. Reduced attention to social cues, such as facial expressions or eye contact, can hinder language acquisition and reciprocity.³⁶ These differences may contribute to difficulties in group activities and collaboration, leading to social withdrawal.⁴⁰

Adolescence

Adolescence involves further refinement of PPS as cognitive and motor regions like the parietal and premotor cortices mature.⁴¹ This development supports participation in sports and complex social interactions, requiring flexible PPS adjustments.

For autistic adolescents, PPS challenges can amplify social and emotional difficulties. Heightened anxiety may constrict PPS boundaries, leading to discomfort in crowded environments. Conversely, reduced spatial awareness can result in boundary violations, affecting peer relationships.⁴² These issues highlight the importance of interventions that address sensory regulation and enhance adaptability.

Adulthood

PPS stabilizes in adulthood as neural circuits supporting multisensory integration mature, though boundaries remain adaptable to experience and environmental demands.²⁸ While PPS flexibility supports spatial navigation and social interaction, autistic adults may struggle with adjusting boundaries in dynamic contexts, leading to sensory-related social difficulties and avoidance of crowded spaces.^{43,44}

These challenges impact various domains, including workplaces, social/romantic relationships, and community participation. Tailored strategies, such as sensory-friendly environments and structured social activities, are essential for supporting adaptive PPS functions.

Old age

In neurotypical aging, PPS expands as a compensatory mechanism for declining motor agility, providing earlier sensory detection of approaching stimuli, which may help mitigate slower reaction times.²⁸ In autistics, this adaptation may coexist with persistent sensory sensitivities, leading to unique PPS alterations. Age-related declines in multisensory integration can further exacerbate sensory processing challenges, making navigation in high-stimulation environments more difficult.¹⁸

Social withdrawal and reduced adaptability to shifting personal space expectations often intensify with age, complicating healthcare access and community participation. These challenges highlight the importance of interventions that address both sensory and motor needs while fostering social inclusion.

PPS dynamics in autism

Building on the developmental variability of PPS discussed across the lifespan, the unique challenges presented by PPS rigidity in autism have profound implications for social interaction and motor coordination. This rigidity can manifest as difficulties in adapting to changing social environments or responding appropriately to social cues.⁴⁵

Inflexible PPS boundaries can limit the ability to interact comfortably and effectively with others, often leading to misunderstandings in social contexts. For instance, an autistic individual with an expanded PPS may require greater personal space during interactions, which neurotypicals might misconstrue as aloofness or shyness. Conversely, a constricted PPS can make social interactions feel overly invasive, resulting in

heightened anxiety and avoidance behaviors. These challenges not only affect interpersonal dynamics but also influence everyday navigation. Crowded spaces can become overwhelming for those with an expanded PPS, while a reduced PPS may lead to misjudged spatial distances, increasing the risk of accidents.^{27,46} Interventions aimed at enhancing PPS flexibility have the potential to improve both social engagement and understanding in such scenarios.

Sensory processing differences, a hallmark of autism, further compound these challenges. Given that PPS represents the sensory space immediately surrounding an individual, disruptions in this representation can significantly influence movement coordination and execution. This connection between PPS disruptions and motor challenges is not unique to autism but is also observed in other neurological conditions. For instance, alterations in PPS have been implicated in the motor symptoms of Parkinson's Disease. Understanding these parallels is particularly relevant in autism, given the increased risk of Parkinsonism due to familial associations and shared genetic risk factors.^{28,47} These insights may illuminate shared mechanisms underlying motor challenges in autism and guide the development of targeted interventions that address both sensory and motor disruptions.

Movement-related difficulties in autism often stem from challenges in integrating somatosensory feedback. Many autistic individuals rely more heavily on visual cues due to atypical functioning in parietal-cerebellar networks, which impacts manual motor control.⁴⁸⁻⁵¹ PPS-focused therapeutic strategies hold promise for improving motor function and overall quality of life by addressing these sensory and motor integration challenges directly.

Table 1 below summarizes the key theoretical findings discussed so far, providing a foundation for exploring the methodological and clinical innovations addressed next.

Area	Findings	Implications
Alterations in PPS Dimensions	Autistics often exhibit less flexible PPS, which is smaller or improperly modulated compared to neurotypicals ⁸ .	Challenges in social communication and interaction with the environment.
Sensory and Motor Coordination ⁵²	Enhanced sensory sensitivities lead to unique PPS manifestations, resulting in rigid or expansive PPS ⁵² .	Complicates personal space management, affecting daily interactions and navigation.
Neural Dynamics	Reduced activity in premotor and parietal cortices; atypical thalamocortical connectivity ^{4,43} .	Contributes to altered spatial perception and heightened sensory experiences.
Behavioral Implications	Atypical PPS correlates with difficulties in social coordination, navigation, and increased anxiety ⁴⁵ .	Highlights the need to incorporate PPS dynamics into assessment and intervention planning for autism.
Developmental Trajectories	PPS evolves differently across life stages, with unique sensory-motor challenges at each phase. (e.g., delayed PPS in infancy).	Age-appropriate interventions to address developmental and contextual sensory needs.
Temporal Dynamics	Delayed synchronization between sensory inputs, such as auditory and tactile stimuli, exacerbates PPS challenges ¹⁸ .	Targeted therapies to improve sensory integration and synchronization for enhanced motor and social responses.
Multisensory Integration	Disruptions in combining sensory inputs impair PPS flexibility and spatial representation ²⁷ .	VR/AR-based tools to train and improve multisensory integration skills.
Environmental Context	Crowded or high-stimulation environments amplify PPS rigidity, leading to anxiety and avoidance behaviors.	Designing sensory-friendly environments to support spatial navigation and reduce stress.

Table 1. Key theoretical insights and implications of PPS research in autism. This table summarizes key findings from the studies on PPS in autism discussed in this review.

Immersive methodologies for PPS research in autism

Building on the theoretical foundations summarized in Table 1, this section explores how immersive technologies such as VR and AR have advanced our understanding of PPS dynamics in autism. These technologies enable researchers to create controlled environments where PPS dynamics can be simulated, manipulated, and studied in detail. Traditional approaches to studying PPS relied on simple sensory detection tasks, such as responding to stimuli near the body,

or experimental techniques like the rubber hand illusion, which explore PPS plasticity and body ownership.⁵³

In autism research, these methods have been adapted to accommodate the unique sensory sensitivities of autistic individuals. VR/AR technologies, in particular, offer customizable and immersive experiences that mitigate sensory overload and anxiety.⁵⁴ By reducing environmental stressors, these tools facilitate a deeper understanding of how autistic

Area	Clinical Insight	Practical Applications
Therapeutic Environments	PPS insights help minimize sensory overload in tailored environments.	Modified classroom seating, workplace adaptations for sensory comfort, and training interventionists/therapists to assess and respect personal space boundaries.
Early Intervention	Sensory over-responsivity in childhood predicts later anxiety ⁵⁵ .	Early sensory regulation interventions to improve long-term emotional and behavioral outcomes.
Social Inclusion	Understanding PPS variations reduces misinterpretation of behaviors.	Educating society about PPS-driven social behaviors to enhance inclusion and reduce misunderstandings.
Intervention Strategies	Tailored interventions to enhance PPS flexibility.	Improve social interactions, reduce anxiety and enhance quality of life.

Table 2. *Clinical insights into PPS in autism.* This table outlines clinical insights into PPS in autism and their corresponding practical applications for therapeutic, social, and intervention strategies.

individuals perceive and interact with their space. Furthermore, immersive technologies can inform the development of interventions that improve spatial awareness, motor coordination, and social engagement.

These immersive methodologies not only deepen our understanding of PPS but also pave the way for practical applications, as explored in the subsequent section on future directions.

Future directions in PPS research and autism

Future research on PPS in autism must build on the clinical insights summarized in Table 2, emphasizing innovative methodologies, interdisciplinary approaches, and the lived experiences of autistic individuals. These directions aim to deepen our understanding of PPS dynamics and translate findings into meaningful applications that improve quality of life.

Expanding research horizons

Innovative methodologies

Building on insights from Table 2, future research should leverage cutting-edge tools like VR and AR technologies to simulate and manipulate dynamic PPS environments. These immersive

technologies allow for the precise measurement of PPS boundaries and provide customizable settings to accommodate sensory sensitivities, offering a pathway to tailored interventions.

In addition, building on the insights from existing studies, my PhD research initiative aims to leverage VR/AR to simulate dynamic PPS environments. By manipulating sensory inputs and tracking behavioral, physiological and neurological responses, we hope to illuminate the specific PPS characteristics that are unique to autism. The addition of neuroimaging techniques like EEG to capture real-time brain activity during PPS-related tasks will provide a better understanding of the neurological processes at play.

Inclusivity in PPS research

While immersive technologies offer powerful tools for studying PPS, addressing the persistent sampling biases is essential to ensure these methodologies capture the full spectrum of autistic experiences. Current research on PPS in autism often excludes higher-support-needs autistics, autistics with communication and behavioral challenges, autistics with intellectual disability, autistics with co-occurring conditions. These exclusions limit the generalizability of findings and prevent a nuanced understanding of how

PPS variability interacts with sensory processing challenges, motor dysfunctions, and co-occurring conditions like seizures.^{56–58} Unlike traditional psychophysical paradigms, VR-based methods offer greater adaptability, reducing barriers to participation and improving accessibility for diverse autistic profiles. Addressing these biases is essential for a more comprehensive understanding of PPS in autism.

Longitudinal studies

Long-term studies are essential to track how PPS evolves across different stages of life. Understanding these developmental trajectories will inform the design of age-appropriate and context-sensitive interventions. For instance, early intervention strategies targeting sensory regulation could mitigate the anxiety linked to sensory over-responsivity and enhance emotional resilience over time.

Interdisciplinary collaboration

Advances in PPS research will require collaboration across fields such as neuroscience, psychology, clinical therapy, and technological innovation. These partnerships can produce holistic models of PPS dynamics, enabling the development of interventions that address sensory, motor, and social challenges simultaneously.

Incorporating lived experiences

Including autistic individuals as active participants in research design ensures ecological validity and aligns interventions with real-world needs. Personal narratives can shed light on how PPS variations impact daily life, offering valuable insights that might be overlooked in purely laboratory-based studies.

Conclusion - bridging research and practice

This review examined how PPS is defined, measured, and modulated in autism, synthesizing developmental, neural, and therapeutic insights. We found that autistics often display atypical PPS representations, affecting social and sensory experiences across the lifespan. Although these

findings underscore the importance of PPS research for autism, limitations such as small and non-representative samples, inconsistent measurement approaches, and the heterogeneity of the autism spectrum warrant caution in generalizing results. The clinical insights summarized in Table 2 highlight the transformative potential of PPS research, from creating sensory-friendly therapeutic environments to fostering greater social inclusion. Future studies must expand on these foundations, integrating advanced methodologies and centering the voices of autistic individuals to develop interventions that are both effective and compassionate.

By embracing these directions, PPS research can achieve dual goals: advancing scientific knowledge while directly improving quality of life for autistic individuals. These efforts not only bridge the gap between theory and practice but also foster greater societal inclusion and understanding.

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